

IMPROVING LEARNERS' PERFORMANCE IN ALL LEARNING AREAS THROUGH PROJECT ALL-IN

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ABSTRACT

Students all throughout the world have experienced considerable learning loss as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, these events have had a tremendous impact on how children learn as well as how teachers work. Teachers have chosen to align with lessons and activities to address this issue of knowledge and ability gaps in students. The objective of this study is to determine the efficacy of adopting PROJECT ALL-IN (Addressing Learning Loss thru Aligning Lessons and Activities across Learning Areas), a strategy for reducing the consequences of learning loss for students of PICAB Elementary School in Infanta, District. Subsequently, to acquire the essential information and data for the study, the researcher acquired and made use of the diagnostic test results from all of the PICAB Elementary School students. Furthermore, Quantitative research was employed to assess the data that had been gathered; therefore, the results of the analysis are then used to draw the conclusions about the efficacy of implementing PROJECT ALL-IN on PICAB Elementary School. The researcher maintains a running total of each student's diagnostic test results. Following this, the researcher got to the conclusion that the student's ability to learn had actually been harmed by the COVID-19 pandemic. On the other hand, it was discovered that the adoption of PROJECT ALL-IN gave the teachers support in resolving the kids' learning loss. Thus, the review concluded that PROJECT ALL-IN's application was successful and satisfied all parties involved, including parents, teachers, and students.

Keywords: *Learning loss, Gaps, Issues, Application, Ability*

INTRODUCTION

“Education is not the filling of a pail, but the lightning of a fire.”

– William Butler Yeals

The COVID-19 pandemic has a significant impact on education systems worldwide, with schools closing for extended periods and transitioning to remote learning. This disruption has resulted in widespread learning loss among learners, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds. Studies have shown that learning loss has been significant in the areas of literacy, numeracy, and social-emotional development (Schleicher, 2020).

To mitigate the effects of learning loss, several strategies have been implemented by educators and policymakers. These strategies include the provision of online learning resources, the use of remedial programs, and the implementation of catch-up programs. However, the effectiveness of these strategies has been mixed, and there is a need for more research to identify the most effective approaches (UNESCO,2021).

Different standardized assessments were conducted and participated by our Filipino learners in the past years. The Philippines’ participation to Program for International Student Assessment (PISA 2018) revealed that the country was way below the average of the participating countries in Mathematics, Science and Reading. The country’s National Achievement Test results for Grade 6, Grade 10 and Grade 12 conducted last 2018 also indicated a very low performance of learners. On the other hand, results of the Regional Learning Assurance for Monitoring and Progress (LAMP) of Regional Learning Outcomes in Distance Learning which was conducted to select Grade 6, Grade 10 and Grade 12 learners revealed that Grade 6 learners manifested a 69.49% Mean Percentage Score while Secondary Junior High School got 68.91 MPS and the Grade 12 got the lowest Mean Percentage Score of 46.78%.

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of providing learners with individualized support to address their specific learning needs. This support can be provided through one-on-one tutoring, small-group instruction, and personalized learning plans. Research has shown that these approaches can be highly effective in addressing learning loss and improving academic outcomes (Valamis 2020).

According to the results of the school’s diagnostic test in all subject areas, the achieved score is only 41.86%, which is less than DepEd standard passing grade of 75%. In this regard, this action research project aims to improve learner's performance through the implementation of Project ALL-IN (Addressing Learning Loss through Aligning Lessons and Activities Across Learning Areas), an innovative teaching approach that promotes integrated and interdisciplinary learning.

Project ALL-IN is a student-centered approach to learning that seeks to bridge the gap between different learning areas by aligning lessons and activities across subjects.

It is designed to promote interdisciplinary learning, critical thinking, and collaborative problem-solving. This approach involves the alignment of lessons and activities across different learning areas to promote a cohesive and interconnected learning experience. Research has shown that this approach can be highly effective in improving academic outcomes and promoting critical thinking skills.

Research Questions

The study aimed to gather information, test, evaluate, and analyze how well PROJECT ALL-IN (Addressing Learning Loss thru Aligning Lessons and Activities across Learning Areas) worked after being implemented to assist the teachers and learners at PICAB Elementary School in addressing learning loss and bridging the gap in learners' knowledge and abilities.

Specifically, the study sought to find out the following:

1. What is the level of learners' performance at PICAB Elementary School before and after the implementation of Project ALL-IN?
2. Is there a significant difference between the level of performance at PICAB Elementary School before and after the implementation of Project ALL-IN?
3. What recommendations for school pedagogical management can be drawn from the study's findings?

METHODOLOGY

Considering the temperament of the study, the researchers employed quantitative research. This investigation utilized a One Group Pre-test Post-test research design as it compared two sets of tests: the pre-test and post-test. According to Reichardt CS (2019), the One Group Pre-test Post-test research design in which the outcome of interest is measured 2 times: once before and once after exposing a non-random group of participants to a certain intervention/treatment.

Sampling

The study utilized purposive sampling. Learners that were guided and teachers that need to implement the PROJECT ALL-IN. Therefore, there were 21 teachers who implemented the project and complete enumeration of the school population from Grade 1-6 or 622 learners served as respondents of this study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers sought first permission from the principal to gather the overall data of learners, sought the participation of other teachers to evaluate the performance of the

learners and secured permission from the learners and parents. After securing all the necessary communication with other parties involved, the researchers conducted the gathering of the diagnostic test results.

Research Instrument

1. Weighted Mean. This was used in analyzing the level of learners' performance before and after the implementation of Project ALL-IN.

The formula is:

$$WM = \frac{\sum x N}{N}$$

Where: WM = Weighted Mean

$\sum x$ = summation of weighted frequencies

N = number of cases

2. Simple Percentage

This was used in analyzing the difference in the learners' performance before and after the implementation of Project ALL-IN. It is the ratio of the occurrence (f) and the total number of the population (N) multiplied by 100.

The computation will be guided by the formula:

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100$$

Where:

P is the computed percentage

f is the frequency of a particular category of a variable

n is the sample

RESULTS

The data in Table 1 presents the results of a pre-test administered to students at PICAB Elementary School across different grade levels before the implementation of Project ALL-IN. The specific question being addressed is the level of learners' performance in various subjects before and after the project.

Table 1. Result of Pre-Test

Grade Level	ESP	AP	FILIPINO	MATH	MAPEH	ENGLISH	MTB	SCIENCE
2	53.84	49.97	42.87	49.18	45.82	42.15	56.90	
3	35.50	38.30	34.63	32.89	37.91	31.82	36.74	38.91

Anderson, T. (2009). Diagnostoc assessment in education: Building on and extending the diagnostic approach. In handbook of research on educational communications and technology (3rd ed., pp.111-124). Routledge. States that the value of diagnostic tests, particularly pre-tests, in education is covered in this chapter. It emphasizes how pre-tests can assist individualized learning and inform instructional decisions.

Table 2. Result of Post-Test

Grade Level	ESP	AP	FILIPINO	MATH	MAPEH	ENGLISH	MTB	SCIENCE
2	75.48	67.66	64.62	57.75	62.75	62.14	67.65	
3	59.69	43.45	53.28	57.24	50.79	57.24	65.4	65.4

Grade Level	ESP	AP	FILIPINO	MATH	MAPEH	ENGLISH	SCIENCE	EPP
4	76.15	60.45	65.56	48.97	56.65	46.08	55.57	54.87
5	82.12	45.69	58.28	43.19	58.57	44.23	53.93	45.69

Grade Level	ESP	AP	FILIPINO	MATH	MAPEH	ENGLISH	SCIENCE	TLE
6	82.97	51.33	69.22	40.44	56.78	51.93	52.03	54.86

Each grade level is represented with the corresponding scores in subjects such as ESP, AP, Filipino, Math, MAPEH, English, Science, and additional subjects like MTB (Mother Tongue-Based), EPP, and TLE (Technology and Livelihood Education).

Specific Question Number 2. Is there a significant difference between the level of performance at PICAB Elementary School before and after the implementation of Project ALL-IN (Addressing Learning Loss thru Aligning Lessons and Activities across Learning Areas)?

Table 3. Difference between Pre-test and Post-Test

Grade Level	ESP	AP	FILIPINO	MATH	MAPEH	ENGLISH	MTB	SCIENCE
2	21.64	17.69	29.99	8.27	16.93	3.93	10.75	
3	24.19	5.15	18.65	24.35	12.88	25.42	28.66	12.27

Grade Level	ESP	AP	FILIPINO	MATH	MAPEH	ENGLISH	SCIENCE	EPP
4	20.87	22.15	30.93	16.08	5.86	14.26	23.39	12.24
5	14.35	14.81	15.82	5.56	16.57	9.39	3.64	13.19

Grade Level	ESP	AP	FILIPINO	MATH	MAPEH	ENGLISH	SCIENCE	TLE
6	25.18	20.15	16.37	8.43	12.42	3.98	1.43	19.08

The result of this study are indicated in Table 3. It showed the difference between the pre-test and post-test. According to the findings, PROJECT ALL-IN was beneficial and suggested as a way to improve students' performance. Where in Grade two learners increased 21.64% in ESP, 17.69% in Araling Panlipunan, 29.99% in Filipino, 8.27% in Mathematics, 16.93% in MAPEH, 3.93% in English, 10.75% in Mother Tongue Based. While for the Grade three learners increased 24.19% in ESP, 5.15% in Araling Panlipunan, 18.65% in Filipino, 24.35% in Mathematics, 12.88% in MAPEH, 25.42% in English, 28.66% in Mother Tongue Based and 12.27% in Science. There is also an increased in Intermediate learners, for grade four there is 20.87% in ESP, 22.15% in Araling Panlipunan, 30.93% in Filipino, 16.08% in Mathematics, 5.86 in MAPEH, 14.26% in English, 23.39% in Science and 12.24% in EPP/TLE. For grade five learners with the increased of 14.35% in ESP, 14.81% in Araling Panlipunan, 15.82% in Filipino, 5.56% in Mathematics, 16.57% in MAPEH, 9.39% in English, 3.64% in Science and 13.19% in EPP/TLE. There is also an increased on grade six learners of 25.18% in ESP, 20.15% in Araling Panlipunan, 16.37% in Filipino, 8.34% in Mathematics, 12.42% in MAPEH, 3.98% in English, 1.43% in Science and 19.08% in EPP/ TLE.

The findings of the study is supported by Borreo (2023) who found out that extensive remediation in a specific learning area is effective in developing pupils' performance. This is evident on his research study where spending an ample time for remediation improved the oral reading performance of the learners.

Specific Question Number 3. What recommendations for school pedagogical management can be drawn from the study's findings?

Therefore, the following recommendations for future researches are indicated.

1. The researchers may continue the PROJECT ALL-IN.
2. Establish a system for ongoing monitoring and evaluation to track the long-term impact of Project ALL-IN on students' academic performance. Regular assessments, feedback loops, and data analysis should be integral parts of this monitoring process.

3. Provide targeted professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their capacity in implementing the aligned lessons and activities. This may include workshops, training sessions, and collaborative planning sessions to share best practices.
 4. Identify subjects or grade levels where improvement was less significant and tailor additional support and resources to address specific challenges. This could involve targeted interventions, specialized teaching strategies, or additional materials.
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DISCUSSION

The data provides a baseline of the learners' performance before the intervention of Project ALL-IN. To assess the impact of the project, a post-test or subsequent data collection after the implementation was done for a comprehensive analysis of the program's effectiveness in addressing learning loss and aligning lessons and activities across learning areas.

According to Pashler H. Rohmer D. Cepeda, N.J & Carpenter, S.K (2007) enhancing learning and retarding forgetting: Choices and consequences. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review* 14(2) 187-193, The impact of post-tests is discussed in this paper along with their contribution to improving learning and lowering forgetfulness, which is pertinent to diagnostic testing. Comparing the pre-test and post-test results, there is a noticeable improvement in the learners' performance in almost all subjects across all grade levels after the implementation of Project ALL-IN. The increase in scores suggests a positive impact of the project on addressing learning loss and aligning lessons and activities across learning areas. The extent of improvement varies across subjects and grade levels, indicating potential areas of strength and areas that may need further attention in future interventions or educational strategies.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing findings the following conclusions had been derived:

1. All learning areas garnered Mean Percentage Scores (MPS) below the national standards, meaning there is a need to implement intervention to improve the performance of the learners.
2. There is a remarkable improvement in the performance of the learners in all learning areas after the implementation of Project ALL-IN.
3. Project ALL-IN is an effective student-centered approach to learning that seeks to bridge the gap between different learning areas by aligning lessons and

activities across subjects. This approach is effectively promotes a cohesive and interconnected learnin experience.

Recommendations

The PROJECT ALL-IN was created as an effective tool and approach for teachers and students of PICAB Elementary School, to make sure that all the students can still learn, and improve their critical thinking and different knowledge on different subjects. In the light of the mentioned findings and conclusions, the following are nearby recommended:

1. To the school head, this study will help them to become aware and will determine what kind of programs, activities and support that is needed to be implemented.
 2. To the teachers, the study will benefit the teachers to enhance their capability in teaching.
 3. The future researchers may use this study as a data source for their research.
 4. Future researchers, can enhance the tools and approach of the PROJECT ALL-IN.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to performing this study, the researcher obtained consent from the appropriate authorities and ensured that the participants' identities and personal information would remain anonymous and secret.

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